

REDUCTION OF DICHROMATE BY HYDROBROMIC AND NITROUS ACIDS IN PRESENCE OF MANGANOUS SULPHATE

BY K. CHATTERJEE AND B. P. GYANI

Hydrobromic and nitrous acids can be titrated potentiometrically with potassium dichromate in presence of strong sulphuric acid (8-12 *N*) and excess manganous sulphate at room temperature (20-22°). Hydrochloric acid is not suitable. Steady potentials are easily attained. Under the experimental conditions the manganous ion is assumed to be first oxidised to manganic ion in spite of the standard oxidation potential of the corresponding electrode being less than that of the $\text{Cr}^{3+}-\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ electrode.⁹ The manganic ion can then oxidise bromide or nitrite ions rapidly. When the sulphuric acid concentration is lower or higher, the figures obtained are less than the correct ones, namely three moles of nitrous acid and six of bromide ions per mole of potassium dichromate.

Direct reduction of dichromate by bromide or nitrite is a slow process. Consequently, it appears that such a titration has not received any notable attention. Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 707), however, found a general increase in the rate of oxidation by dichromate in presence of manganous sulphate. Bobtelsky and Glasner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1376) studied the rate of oxidation of hydrobromic acid by chromic acid and found this rate to increase greatly in presence of MnSO_4 . None of these authors explored the possibility of using these reactions for analytical procedures. We therefore took up the titrations mentioned above.

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus and procedure were similar to those employed previously by Gyani and Prasad (this *Journal*, 1955, 82, 313). A.R. quality of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ and KBr and pure recrystallised NaNO_2 were used. The titrations were all performed at the room temperature (20-22°).

The Reaction between Dichromate and KBr in presence of Mn^{2+} .—0.005 *M*- $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (100 c.c.) was titrated with *M*- KBr in presence of 0.3 *M*- MnSO_4 , in the following H_2SO_4 concentrations: (A) 14*N*, (B) 12*N*, (C) 10*N*, (D) 8*N*, (E) 6*N*. The corresponding curves are shown in Fig. 1. Some of these titrations were repeated in presence of 0.05 *M*- MnSO_4 . Curve (F) is typical of titrations in 4.6 *N* HCl or 8*N*- H_2SO_4 saturated with KCl .

FIG. 1
Bromide-dichromate.

A deep cherry-red colour appeared on mixing the dichromate and $MnSO_4$ solutions. As this indicated oxidation of Mn^{2+} to Mn^{3+} , the reaction mixtures were stored in a dark place for a few hours before titration to complete the oxidation process. In (A) and (B), the mixtures were immediately titrated as a precipitate appeared on keeping. (E) and the mixtures containing $0.05N$ - $MnSO_4$ had to be stored for a day since the oxidation appeared to be slow. Brown vapours of bromine appeared and the red colour decreased as the bromide solution was gradually added.

Steady potentials were quickly set up in high concentrations of H_2SO_4 up to $8N$. Nearly 15-20 minutes were, however, required for the potentials to be steady near the equivalence point. The equilibrium was slow at lower concentrations of acid or $MnSO_4$. In presence of HCl the potentials were never steady. The curve (F) refers to a rapid titration.

In (B) to (D) inflections correspond to six moles of KBr per mole dichromate. The inflection in (A) was at 5 moles and in (E) at 4.5 moles. Curves were more and more steeply inflected as the acid concentration increased. Titrations in lower acid concentrations ($6N$) and lower $MnSO_4$ concentrations ($0.05M$) were not only slow but the reproducibility was also poor. (F) was the poorest in these respects.

The Reaction between Dichromate and Nitrite.—Titrations of 100 c.c. of $0.005M$ dichromate ($0.3M$ - $MnSO_4$) with M - $NaNO_2$ were carried out in presence of the following H_2SO_4 concentrations: (A) $14N$, (B) $12N$, (C) $10N$, (D) $8N$ and (E) $6N$; and

of HCl concentrations: (F) 5 N and (G) 4.5 M. The corresponding graphs appear in Fig. 2. Some of these titrations were repeated in 0.05 M-MnSO₄ and also in lower concentrations of sulphuric acid (less than 6 N).

FIG. 2

Nitrite-dichromate.

'Appearance of the cherry-red colour and attainment of equilibrium are governed by the same factors discussed in connection with bromide. The mixtures had therefore to be stored as before. The colour change at the equivalence point was, however, much sharper, from deep red to emerald-green. In (B) to (D), steep inflections at three moles of NaNO₂ per mole of dichromate were obtained. In (A), (E), (F) and (G) the inflections were at 2.75, 2.90, 2.40 and 2.80 moles respectively. Titrations in lower acid concentrations or MnSO₄ concentrations were again of little practical value.

DISCUSSION

Inflections at 6 moles KBr and 3 moles NaNO₂ may correspond to the following reactions:

Bromide and nitrite are, however, oxidised rapidly and quantitatively only in presence of MnSO₄. The development of the characteristic red colour and its disappearance at the equivalence point, revealing the green colour of Cr³⁺, suggest that bromide and nitrite are oxidised by Mn³⁺, an equivalent quantity of which is produced in the first place by oxidation of Mn²⁺ by Cr₂O₇²⁻. The action of Mn³⁺ may be represented by the following equations:

- (iii) $K_2Cr_2O_7 + 6MnSO_4 + 7H_2SO_4 \rightleftharpoons Cr_2(SO_4)_3 + 3Mn_2(SO_4)_3 + K_2SO_4 + 7H_2O$
 (iv) $3Mn_2(SO_4)_3 + 6KBr = 6MnSO_4 + 3Br_2 + 3K_2SO_4$
 (v) $3Mn_2(SO_4)_3 + 3NaNO_2 + 3H_2O = 3NaNO_3 + 6MnSO_4 + 3H_2SO_4$

It will be seen that all the Mn^{3+} are reduced back to Mn^{2+} and the total concentration of the same does not change when the reactions are completed. The part played by the Mn^{3+} is therefore truly catalytic.

Table I records the standard oxidation potentials of the reactions concerned (Latimer, "The Oxidation States of Elements and their Potentials in Aqueous Solutions" pp. 340-45, Prentice-Hall, New York, 1952).

TABLE I

Reaction.	E°_{25} .	Reaction.	E°_{25} .
$Mn^{2+} = Mn^{3+} + e$	-1.51	$2Br^- = Br_2(liq) + 2e$	-1.07
$2Cr^{3+} + 7H_2O = Cr_2O_7^{2-} + 14H^+ + 6e$	-1.33	$HNO_2 + H_2O = NO_2^- + 3H^+ + 2e$	-0.94

The oxidation potential of $Cr^{3+} - 3Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ is higher than that of $Mn^{2+} - Mn^{3+}$. In a solution of unit activities of the ions (in absence of extraneous ions) therefore there is not much possibility of oxidation of Mn^{2+} . There is little doubt from our observations that such an oxidation does take place before the titration is started. The oxidation potential of $Mn^{2+} - Mn^{3+}$ must therefore be increased to a value less negative than -1.33 under the actual experimental conditions. A consideration of the general equation

$$E = E^\circ + \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{[\text{oxid}]}{[\text{red}]}$$

shows that either E° is higher than E° , the standard potential in absence of acid and other ions or [red] is unduly reduced. This latter is possible if Mn^{2+} forms a complex with the bisulphate ion as suggested by Fales and Roller (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 345). Since a large amount of $MnSO_4$ is required, the action of $Mn^{2+} - Mn^{3+}$ is not like that of $Ce^{3+} - Ce^{4+}$ in establishing a quick equilibrium in redox titrations. It appears that the altered value of E must yet be more negative than those of experimental oxidation potentials of $Br^- - Br_2$ or $NO_2^- - NO_3^-$ to produce the required oxidations. This is fortunate since the possibility of removal of these ions (by complex formation or otherwise) cannot be ruled out. Bobtelsky (*loc. cit.*) points out that the reaction $Mn^{3+} + Br^- \rightarrow Mn^{2+} + \frac{1}{2}Br_2$ involves a direct removal of electron from the Br^- , making a rapid reaction possible.

The above considerations help to understand why sulphuric acid concentrations have to be properly adjusted (8-12 N) as also the amount of $MnSO_4$ to be added. Neglect of these leads immediately to a failure of titration in both the cases. Incidentally, a full investigation of the four electrodes listed in Table I is called for.